

Echoes from the Fenceline
by Lance Corporal Brian Paul Kaess¹

"Nightly from their azure towers, to keep watch above the Flowers." -Edgar Allen Poe

"The Mouth of the bay opened to the Caribbean Sea,
Astride the Promontories lay Ocean a turquoise Blue-green.
Standing guard at the Fenceline was my sentinel's task,
A buzzards song rang out amid a brazen pass.
The No-Man's land lay tranquil and serene,
The Stoics themselves might well have been pleased.
Glistening calm and glistening light,
Is the world implacable, let nature decide.
Adelante! Adelante! Columbus' Lieutenant had railed,
From the Underworld Odysseus himself might have sailed.
Am I eager to leave this verdant, emerald Isle,
If only to feel the warmth of laughter awhile.
But fulsome encomiums are inimical to my dreams,
While Hurricanes blast forth in perennial streams.
No Cesar Borgia, Caligula, or Capone buried here,
But the likes of Che', Castro's Mother, and other Communist Fare.
No alpine meadow, or primrose valley adorned,
But a tender Glen might not yet be scorned.
No garland to gather from the sugar cane,
But a look of despair that melts in the Rain.
Whispering shadows and murmuring light,
Sunsets that echo a Heavenly sight.

¹ This poem was written by Brian Paul Kaess for the Annual Poetry Contest at the U.S. Naval Base in Guantanamo Bay, Cuba, in 1998. Brian was stationed in the U.S. Marines at this time and was working as a radio operator on the Windward side of the base.